

INFLUENCE OF WOLLASTONITE ON HYDRATION AND PROPERTIES OF MAGNESIUM POTASSIUM PHOSPHATE CEMENTS

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Abstract. *This study investigates the effect of wollastonite on the hydration and properties of magnesium potassium phosphate (MKP) cements. In MKP cements some efflorescence can occur; the presence of wollastonite suppresses efflorescence as the formation of $Mg_2KH(PO_4)_2 \cdot 15H_2O$ is prevented. The presence of wollastonite leads also to more heat (per g of MKP cement) due to the filler effect and due to the reaction of wollastonite, which increases strength, especially at low water-to-binder (w/b) ratio of 0.25 and at later ages, and lowers the pH values in the cement pore solution. The reaction of wollastonite does not lead to the formation of crystalline hydrates, both experimental and thermodynamic findings suggest the formation of amorphous hydroxyapatite and magnesium silicate hydrates (M-S-H).*

Keywords: *magnesium potassium phosphate (mkp), cement, wollastonite, reactivity, hydration, strength.*

Introduction. Magnesium potassium phosphate (MKP) cements, which harden through an acid-base reaction between calcined magnesia (MgO) and potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄), is an alternative to Portland cement (PC). Compared to PC, MKP cements have the advantage of fast setting [1,2], high early strength [3], low shrinkage [2], strong bonding with PC substrates [2], low pH [4–6], strong encapsulation capacity on heavy metals [7,8], and good biocompatibility [9,10]. They are used for various applications, such as rapid repair materials for damaged infrastructure [2,11,12], as solidification/stabilization agents for wastes containing heavy metals [1,7,8], and as potential binders for immobilizing low-level nuclear wastes [13–15]. Recent research involved also their use in medical technology due to their good biocompatibility and antibacterial properties [9,10]. The hydration reaction of MKP cements can be changed by using different magnesium-to-phosphate (Mg/PO₄) molar ratios [6,16], water-to-cement (w/c) ratios [4–6,16], retarders [4], and mineral additions [14,17,18]. The dominant hardening reaction of MKP cements is described as

(1) As shown in Eq. (1), magnesium potassium phosphate hexahydrate (MgKPO₄·6H₂O, K-struvite) is the stoichiometric reaction product of hydrated MKP cements providing strength. Furthermore, hydration of MKP cements is exothermic with strong heat release (QHeat), which not only accelerates cement hardening, but also makes cement applications in large scales difficult [1,19]. To slow down cement hydration kinetics and to control heat release, different methods have been used, such as i) use of retarders like borax [2] and boric acid [4,14], ii) decrease of magnesia reactivity [20], iii) increase of initial pH by partially replacing KH₂PO₄ with K₂HPO₄ or

Na₂HPO₄·12H₂O [21,22], and iv) cement dilution using mineral additions, such as fly ash [3,14,15,17], silica fume [23,24], metakaolin [18], and wollastonite [1,25,26]. Wollastonite (CaSiO₃) is an inosilicate mineral and has been used in cementitious materials for decades [27–30]. It has microfiber-like particles, which effectively increased flexural strength and fracture toughness of PC-based materials due to an enhanced crack resistance [27,28]. However, wollastonite shows no or only little reaction in PC matrices [27,28], which is probably due to the high pH of pore solution of around 13–14 [31], where wollastonite is more stable than C-S-H and thus not reactive. At low pH wollastonite is better soluble and can release calcium and silicate ions. Therefore, wollastonite has been used as raw material for producing low pH cements, such as inorganic phosphate cements (ceramics) [32–35], carbonated wollastonite-based materials [30,36], and MKP cements [1,25,26]. The blend of wollastonite with MKP cements was reported to reduce heat generation [1], to increase mechanical strength [1], and to improve heat resistance under high temperatures [25]. Moreover, it has been assumed that wollastonite reacts with potassium and phosphate from the MKP cements and leads to formation of brushite (CaHPO₄·2H₂O) and potassium metasilicate (K₂SiO₃) [1,26]; however, experimental evidence is missing.

Table 1

Chemical composition of raw materials wt%.

Materials	MgO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	TiO ₂	SO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	CO ₂ ^a	L.O. ^b
Magnesia	93.54	4.37	0.04	0.15	1.62	0.02	0.0	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.18	0.18
Wollastonite	0.41	51.86	0.86	0.19	44.15	0.12	0.31	0.01	0.05	0.00	0.50	1.99
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.45	2.01	0.3	0.00	0.06	36.63	0.28	0.02	0.02	40.44	n.d. ^c	20.94

a) CO₂ content was calculated based on the total carbon content determined by combustion analyses. b) Loss on ignition. c) not detected.

As only limited information regarding the reactivity of wollastonite and the resultant additional hydrates are available, this study investigates the effect of wollastonite (i) on the strength of MKP cements at low water-to-binder (w/b) ratios of 0.25 and 0.5, and (ii) on the hydration at w/b ratios of 0.5 and 5, which were characterized by isothermal calorimetry and determination of cement hydrate assemblage and pore solution chemistry.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and mix designs The starting materials included dead-burnt magnesia (MgO), wollastonite (CaSiO₃), quartz powder, and KH₂PO₄ in technical grades, and magnesium chloride (MgCl₂) in chemical grade. Chemical compositions of magnesia, wollastonite and KH₂PO₄ determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis are given in Table 1. Mineralogical composition of magnesia and wollastonite was determined by X-ray diffraction method (XRD, CoKα, Panalytical X'Pert Pro). Magnesia contains a main phase of periclase (MgO) and minor impurities of forsterite (Mg₂SiO₄) and monticellite (CaMgSiO₄). Wollastonite contains a main phase of 'wollastonite-2 M' (CaSiO₃) and traces of quartz (SiO₂) and calcite (CaCO₃). The characterization using secondary electron microscopy (SEM, ESEM Quanta FEG 650) shows a microfiber-like shape of most wollastonite particles. The median particle diameters (d₅₀) of magnesia, wollastonite and KH₂PO₄ measured by a laser particle size analyzer (Malvern

Mastersizer X) are 19.0 ± 0.3 , 3.7 ± 0.5 , and 34.4 ± 4.8 μm , respectively. Mix proportions used in this study are present in Table 2. Three systems were studied: A) cement pastes with a Mg/PO_4 molar ratio of 2.7 and w/b ratios in a range of 0.25–0.83; B) cement suspension with the same Mg/PO_4 molar ratio of 2.7 and w/b ratio of 5, and C) suspensions of wollastonite blended with KH_2PO_4 , magnesia or MgCl_2 , which have w/b ratios of 5.2 and 6.8. All the samples were cured at 20 °C, except the suspensions of wollastonite mixed with magnesia (WMgO-S) or MgCl_2 (W-MgCl-S) at 50 °C. 2.2. Methods 2.2.1. Compressive and flexural strength According to the mix proportions given in Table 2, the powder components of the samples (2.7-C-P025, 2.7-W-P025, and 2.7-W-P05) were weighted and well dry-mixed for 1 min. After that, deionized water was added and wet-mixing using a vacuum mixer was carried out at a speed of 250 rpm for 2 min. Fresh mixtures were cast in molds with dimensions of $20 \times 20 \times 100$ mm^3 . All the samples were cured in air at 20 °C and relative humidity (RH) of 70% until strength test after 3, 7, 28, 72, 200, 690, and 850 days. A three-point bending test was carried

Table 2

Mix proportions of wollastonite-magnesium-phosphate systems referred to 1g KH_2PO_4 .

Sample	Mg/PO ₄ ratio ^a	w/b ratio	w/c ratio	Wollastonite	KH ₂ PO ₄	Magnesia	MgCl ₂	Quartz powder	Water	tFS [min] A)
MKP cement pastes										
2.7C PO25	2.7	0.25	0.25	-	1.0	0.8	-	-	0.45	11±2
2.7C PO25	2.7	0.25	0.42	1.2	1.0	0.8	-	-	0.75	36±5
2.7C PO25	2.7	0.5	0.5	-	1.0	0.8	-	-	0.9	-
2.7C PO25	2.7	0.5	0.83	1.2	1.0	0.8	-	-	1.5	-
2.7C PO25	2.7	0.5	0.83	-	1.0	0.8	-	1.2	1.5	-
2.7C PO25	2.7	0.83	0.83	-	1.0	0.8	-	-	1.5	-

A. Molar ratio.

B. w/b denotes water-to binder mass ratio. For MKP cement systems, binder refers to sum of magnesia, KH_2PO_4 , and wollastonite (quartz). w/c denotes water-to cement ratio, and cement refers to sum of magnesia and KH_2PO_4 . For wollastonite - KH_2PO_4 (MgO/MgCl_2) suspension, binder refers to sum of wollastonite and KH_2PO_4 (magnesia or MgCl_2).

C. Analyses of final setting time (tFS), compressive and flexural strength. Final setting time was measured by Vicat needle test using fresh paste around 200 g.

D. Analyses of calorimetry and determination of hydrate assemblage and pore solution chemistry. Also, compressive and flexural strength of 2.7-W-P05 was determined.

E. Calorimetry only.

F. Analyses of calorimetry, pH/electrical conductivity, and determinations of hydrate assemblages and pore solution chemistry.

G. Determination of hydrate assemblages. Mass ratio between wollastonite and KH_2PO_4 of W-K-S was kept consistent with that of 2.7-W-S5. W-K-S was cured at 20 °C up to 340 days. Ratios between KH_2PO_4 and magnesia (W-MgO-S) or MgCl_2 (W-MgCl-S) were used to guarantee sufficient magnesium source in water. To accelerate potential chemical reactions, they were cured at 50 °C for 110 and 180 days, respectively.

Solubility products ($\log K_{so}^\circ$) of calcium, magnesium, phosphate and potassium containing solids at standard conditions 25 °C and 1 bar.

Species $\log K_{so}^\circ$ a Refb

Octacalcium phosphate:

C-S-H (CSHQ solid solution)

(CaO)0.67SiO₂(H₂O)1.5:

(CaO)0.83(SiO₂)0.67(H₂O)1.83:

(CaO)1.33SiO₂(H₂O)2.17:

(CaO)1.5(SiO₂)0.67(H₂O)2.5:

M-S-H (M-C-S-H solid solution)

b ts: calculated in this study, see Appendix A. out first using a span of 60 mm at a loading rate of 20 N/s. Two prisms were measured for each paste after each specific curing age. After that,

the obtained four prism halves were used for compressive strength measurement at a loading rate of 1 MPa/s using a contact surface area of 20 20 mm².

Isothermal calorimetry

As specified in Table 2, heat flow of the cement pastes with w/b ratios of 0.5 and 0.83 were measured using isothermal conduction calorimetry (TA instrument, TAM Air) at 20 °C. Powder components were weighted into Admix ampoule and well dry-mixed for 1 min. After thermal equilibration, deionized water was injected into Admix ampoule, and the mixture was wet-mixed for 2 min. Note that segregation could occur in samples at high w/b ratio.

X-ray diffraction and thermogravimetric analyses To analyze hydrate assemblage, cement hydration was stopped after specific curing ages. Suspension samples were filtered using a Büchner funnel under vacuum. The remaining solids were soaked in isopropanol for around 15 min. Afterwards isopropanol was removed by filtration, and diethyl ether was used to rinse the solids and removed by filtration as well. The solids were then dried at 40 °C for around 10 min to remove any remaining organic solvents, and stored in sealed bottles. Paste samples were gently crushed into small pieces first, and the same hydration stoppage protocol was then applied. The stopped samples were further ground by hand to a grain size < 63 µm before XRD and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). XRD analyses were performed with a Panalytical X'pert Pro in a Θ - Θ configuration using CoK α radiation and the X'Celerator detector. The samples were scanned between 5° and 90° 2 θ for 45 min. Wollastonite and magnesia consumptions in hydrated samples were assessed semi-quantitatively by fitting peak areas in X'Pert Highscore Plus software using CaF₂ as an external standard for the intensity correction.

Fig. 2. A) Compressive and B) flexural strengths of pastes with (2.7-W-P025, 2.7-W-P05)/without (2.7-C-P025) wollastonite at w/b ratios of 0.25 and 0.5. Strengths of the reference paste without wollastonite (2.7-C-P025) at w/b ratio of 0.25 were taken from [6].

Reaction degrees of magnesia (2.7-C-P05 and 2.7-W-P05 after 28 days) and wollastonite (2.7-W-P05 from 5 h to 420 days) were estimated by comparing the corrected peak intensities between unhydrated and hydrated samples. In consideration of fast dissolution of KH_2PO_4 at high w/b ratio of 5, reaction degree of wollastonite in 2.7-W-S5 from 22 min to 150 days were estimated by comparing the corrected peak intensities between the sample after 5 min of hydration and the rest hydrated samples. After quantification, all the results were further corrected according to [37] for bound water based on TGA result at 600 °C. TGA was carried out using Mettler Toledo TGA/SDTA 815e device from 30 to 1000 °C at heating rate of 20 °C/min under nitrogen atmosphere.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) analysis

Solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra of K-struvite [16], potassium calcium hydrogen phosphate ($\text{CaK}_3\text{H}(\text{PO}_4)_2$) [6], un-hydrated cement with wollastonite (2.7-W-P05), and hydrated cements (2.7-C-P05, 2.7-W-P05, and 2.7-W-S5) were collected on a Bruker AV III HD 400 MHz widebore spectrometer. ^{29}Si MAS NMR spectra were collected using a probe of 7 mm, at 79.505 MHz at a spinning speed of KHz with a plus duration of 2.5 μs . ^{31}P MAS NMR spectra were collected using a probe of 2.5 mm, at 161.995 MHz at a spinning speed of 20 KHz with a plus duration of 2.5 μs . ^{29}Si and ^{31}P chemical shifts are referenced to external samples of tetramethylsilane ($\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_4$) and ammonium dihydrogen phosphate ($\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$), respectively.

Fig. 3. A) Heat flow, B) cumulative heat of the hydrated pastes (2.7-C-P05, 2.7-C-P08, 2.7-W-P05, and 2.7-Q-P05) after 48 h. Results of the heat flow and cumulative heat are normalized to the weight of magnesia plus KH_2PO_4 , which is referred to as ‘cement’ in the unit of the Y-axis.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Backscattered electron (BSE) imaging coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analysis was carried out on cement polished sections. Hydration stoppage protocol for cement suspension as described above was applied to 2.7-W-S5 after 150 days. The stopped powder sample was first mixed with a low-viscosity epoxy resin; after that, the hardened resin was cut, polished, coated with 10 nm carbon. For 2.7-W-P05, paste sample with a diameter of 20 mm and a height of 15 mm after 420 days was cut from center of a cylinder, and soaked in isopropanol for one week first and dried in oven at 40 °C for two weeks. After that, it was impregnated with the same low-viscosity epoxy resin and applied with the same procedures for cutting, polishing and carbon coating. The conduction of SEM was under high vacuum mode ($3\text{--}4 \times 10^{-6}$ Pa) with an accelerating voltage of 10–15 kV.

Electrical conductivity and pH

The changes of electrical conductivity and pH in hydrated cement suspensions (2.7-C-S5 and 2.7-W-S5) were monitored in real time using the setup detailed in [16]. The pH electrode (Mettler Toledo) was calibrated against pH buffers at pH 4, 7, 9, and 12 before each measurement. As detailed in [16], cement suspension was filled in a vessel with a lid tightly locked to avoid possible carbonation and water evaporation. A water bath at 20 °C was used to ensure a stable thermal condition during test. Cement suspension was continuously stirred by an overhead stirrer. The measured data was automatically recorded at time steps of 1 min.

Ion activities and elemental concentrations

K^+ - and Mg^{2+} -selective electrodes and the setup presented above for the electrical conductivity and pH measurement were used to measure K^+ and Mg^{2+} activities in hydrated cement suspensions (2.7-C-S5 and 2.7-W-S5). The K^+ -selective electrode (perfect ION™ comb K Lemo) was calibrated against KH_2PO_4 standard solutions at 0.0044, 0.04, 0.22, 0.43, 0.48, and 0.77 M. Hydrate precipitations on the surface of the Mg^{2+} -selective electrode (DX244-Mg) could affect the measured value, therefore, measured raw data in mV instead of absolute concentrations are given in this study.

Fig. 4. Calculated hydrate assemblage in 2.7-W-P05 as a function of wollastonite reaction degree (α_w). The thermodynamic data compiled in [Table 3](#) were used and a reaction degree of 36% for MgO was used according to the experimentally observed reaction degree of MgO (see below).

Ion chromatography (IC, Dionex, DP series ICS-3000) was used to measure the total ion concentrations in liquid phase of cements. Solution of the cement suspensions (2.7-C-S5 and 2.7-W-S5) was obtained using a nylon filter with a mesh size of 0.45 μm . Pore solution of the hardened cement pastes (2.7-C-P05 and 2.7-W-P05) were extracted from samples cast in 500 mL polyethylene bottles (sealed curing at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) by the steel die method [31,38], and filtered using the same type of nylon filter. One part of the solution was diluted using Milli-Q water (ultra-pure water) for IC measurement, and the other part was used undiluted for pH measurement (Meter 766). The pH meter was calibrated against pH buffers at pH 4, 7, 9, and 12.

Thermodynamic modelling

The calculation of saturation indices from measured aqueous concentrations allows to assess whether the pore solution is saturated with respect to different hydrates, which thus may precipitate as discussed in detail e.g. in [39]. If the pore solution is oversaturated with respect to a certain solid, the solid is likely to precipitate; while undersaturation indicates that a solid is unlikely to precipitate or that it dissolves. The saturation index (SI) of a solid corresponds to $\text{SI} = \log \text{IAP}/K_{\text{so}}$. The ion activity product (IAP) is calculated based on the measured concentrations in solution and K_{so} represents the theoretical solubility product of the solid. As the use of saturation indices can be misleading when comparing phases which dissociate into a different number of ions, “effective” saturation indices were calculated where the saturation indices was divided by the number of ions participating in the reactions to form the solids [31,39], i.e., the saturation indices for brucite, newberyite, phosphorösslerite, K-struvite, $\text{Mg}_2\text{KH}(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mg}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, bobierrite, cattite, brushite, octacalcium phosphate, hydroxyapatite, and $\text{CaK}_3\text{H}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ are divided by 3, 3, 3, 3, 6, 5, 5, 5, 3, 16, 9, and 7. The formation from the ions Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , PO_4^{3-} , SiO_4^{2-} , K^+ , and H^+ was considered but not the influence of H_2O .

Fig. 5. XRD patterns of the hydrated pastes: A) reference paste without wollastonite at w/b ratio of 0.5 (2.7-C-P05), B) paste with wollastonite at w/b ratio of 0.5 (2.7-W-P05), and C) estimated reaction degree of wollastonite corrected for bound water based on TGA results at 600 °C. P = periclase, K = KH_2PO_4 , Q = quartz, S = K-struvite, W = wollastonite-2 M, 15 = $\text{Mg}_2\text{KH}(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$, * = unidentified phase.

Fig. 6. TGA/DTG of hydrated MKP cements with time: A) without wollastonite (2.7-C-P05) and B) with wollastonite (2.7-W-P05). 15 = $\text{Mg}_2\text{KH}(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$, * = unidentified phase.

The geochemical GEMS-PSI software [40] together with the PSI thermodynamic database [41], the cement-specific Cemdata18 [42] and the recently compiled database of magnesium (potassium) phosphates [43], extended with data for calcium phosphates and M-C-S-H [44], were used for the calculation as summarized in Table 3. The lower solubility of the calcium phosphate solids in Table 3 indicate an even higher stability of calcium phosphate than of Mg-phosphates solids and thus a tendency for the formation of calcium phosphates in the presence of calcium.

Results and discussion

Cement pastes. Segregation and strength development

The appearances of the MKP cement paste samples with/without wollastonite at w/b ratios of 0.25 and 0.5 are displayed in Fig. 1. The reference paste samples without wollastonite (2.7-C-P05 and 2.7-C-P025) show clear segregations, especially at w/b of 0.5. At high w/b ratio magnesia particles preferably segregate due to the higher density compared to KH_2PO_4 , which leads to a higher w/b ratio and a lower Mg/PO_4 molar ratio at the upper part of the sample causing the formation of efflorescence [6].

Fig. 7. A) ^{31}P NMR spectra of K-struvite, $\text{CaK}_3\text{H}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and hydrated cements, B) ^{29}Si NMR spectra of unhydrated (2.7-W: unhydrated) and hydrated (2.7-W-P05) cements with wollastonite.

S = K-struvite, K = KH_2PO_4 , C_{at} = cattite, C_K = $\text{CaK}_3\text{H}(\text{PO}_4)_2$, P₇ = phosphorösslerite, 15 = $\text{Mg}_2\text{KH}(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$. * = unidentified phase. The equilibrium times for K-struvite, $\text{CaK}_3\text{H}(\text{PO}_4)_2$, 2.7-C-P05, 2.7-W-P05, and 2.7-W-S05 were 740, 50, 28, 420, and 150 days, respectively. The synthesis of K-struvite is detailed in [6] and that of $\text{CaK}_3\text{H}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in Appendix A.

The partial replacement of cement with wollastonite prevents the segregation as well as the efflorescence, which is attributed to the smaller particle size of wollastonite and/or potential chemical reactions occurring during setting and hardening. As indicated in Table 2, the paste with

wollastonite at w/b ratio of 0.25 (2.7-W-P025) has longer final setting time than the reference paste without wollastonite (2.7-C-P025), which is probably due to the dilution of the cement by wollastonite.

[Fig. 2](#) shows the strength developments of the pastes at w/b ratios of 0.25 and 0.5. Strengths of the reference paste without wollastonite at w/b ratio of 0.5 (2.7-C-P05) were not measured due to the strong segregation as shown in [Fig. 1](#). As detailed in [6], strengths of 2.7-C-P025 increase first up to 7 days and decrease thereafter due to volume expansion and resulting crack formations. For the pastes with wollastonite, the decrease of w/b ratio from 0.5 to 0.25 strongly increases compressive and flexural strengths. The strengths of the sample with wollastonite, 2.7-W-P025, are up to 7 days lower than that of 2.7-C-P025, but much higher after 28 days and later. The continuous strength increase of 2.7-W-P025 with time indicates a continuing condensed microstructure.

Isothermal calorimetry

The results of isothermal calorimetry are shown in [Fig. 3](#). Quartz powder was used as a reference to distinguish between the effect of additional water and surface on cement hydration (filler effect) and the contribution of the reaction of wollastonite. As displayed in [Fig. 3A](#) and [B](#), the release of hydration heat is almost finished after 48 h, and the main hydration reactions occur during the first 8 h. During the first few minutes endothermic heat events are observed for all pastes due to the dissolution of KH_2PO_4 in water, and the higher endothermic heat events of the pastes with wollastonite or quartz powder (2.7-W-P05 and 2.7-Q-P05) are due to their higher w/c ratio of 0.83 as given in [Table 2](#). The first exothermic peak is comparable for all the pastes. The second exothermic peaks of 2.7-W-P05 and 2.7-Q-P05 show higher intensity and are shifted to earlier hydration time as compared to the corresponding 2.7-C-P05. Moreover, 2.7-W-P05 shows the highest cumulative heat up to 48 h, which can be partially attributed to the filler effect of wollastonite, similar to the filler effect of quartz powder in PC [48]. In fact, the higher cumulative heat per g cement of the reference paste with quartz (2.7-Q-P05) shows that the additional water and/or nucleation sites on the quartz surface enhance MKP reaction. The cumulative heat after 48 h of the sample (2.7-C-P08), which has the same w/c of 0.83 as the samples with quartz or wollastonite at w/b = 0.5, is somewhat lower ([Fig. 3B](#)) as a higher fraction of potassium and phosphate remain in solution, indicating that the presence of additional nucleation sites on the quartz (and wollastonite) surface play an important role for the cement reaction. The higher total heat of the wollastonite containing sample (2.7-W-P05) indicates that wollastonite contributes to heat of hydration due to participation in the chemical reactions.

Conclusions

This study investigated the effect of wollastonite on the hydration and properties of MKP cements. Based on the presented findings, the following conclusions can be drawn. The presence of wollastonite can prevent cement segregation at high w/b ratio and suppress efflorescence. Wollastonite also increased compressive and flexural strength, in particular after 28 days and longer, due to the reaction of wollastonite with the magnesium and phosphate. Thermodynamic calculations indicated that the reaction of wollastonite in an MKP cement is expected to lead to the partial destabilization of K-struvite and to the formation of M(-C)-S-H and hydroxyapatite. Experimental evidences of cement hydrate assemblages from ^{31}P , ^{29}Si NMR and SEM/EDS analyses confirm the reaction of wollastonite in cement and suggest hydroxyapatite (amorphous) and M-S-H to be the main hydrates in addition to K-struvite. Also the calculation of saturation

indices based on the measured composition of the aqueous phase point towards the precipitation of hydroxyapatite and M-S-H in MKP cement with wollastonite present. The formation of hydroxyapatite and M-S-H was also observed in additional experiments, where wollastonite reacted with only KH_2PO_4 or with only MgCl_2 . With only KH_2PO_4 wollastonite reacted to hydroxyapatite and Mg Cl_2 to M-(-C)-S-H.

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